

IBISBA 1.0

Industrial Biotechnology Innovation and Synthetic Biology Accelerator

Deliverable D7.4

BPM Demonstrator

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Table of contents

1. Context.....	4
2. Introduction	5
Terminology	6
Scope Assessment.....	6
Selection of BPM System	6
Demonstration	7
3. Recommendations	9
4. Lessons learnt	9
Granularity of Enactment	9
Single Facility Interpretation.....	10
Sub-contracting Facility Interpretation.....	10
Multi-facility Interpretation	10
Granularity Summary.....	10
Documentation	11
Forms	11
Extension of BPM Activity.....	11
5. Partners involved in the work.....	11
6. Annexes.....	12
a. <i>Annex A: Comparison of BPM Systems</i>	12
b. <i>Annex B: Architecture and Implementation</i>	14
Overall Architecture.....	14
MoSCoW Assessment	15
Extensions to IBISBAHub.....	16
Implementation	18

Figures

Figure 1 Demonstration project.....	7
Figure 2 Completed project	8
Figure 3 BPMN extensions	17
Figure 4 Overall Implementation	18
Figure 5 Project registered on the Hub.....	19
Figure 6 Overview of the Aspergillus Project.....	19
Figure 7 Generation of draft BPM model	20
Figure 8 Draft BPM model.....	22
Figure 9 Start BPM Application	23
Figure 10 Initial Summary Report.....	23
Figure 11 Start Sentry	24
Figure 12 Start Sentry Notification	24
Figure 13 Start Sentry Form	25
Figure 14 Start Sentry Form for Assay	25
Figure 15 Notes uploaded to the Hub.....	26
Figure 16 Updated status report.....	27
Figure 17 Finish Sentry.....	27
Figure 18 Finish Sentry Notification.....	27
Figure 19 Finish Sentry Form for Assay.....	28
Figure 20 Proteins detected placeholder satisfied	29
Figure 21 Uploaded proteins	29
Figure 22 Completed Project	30

1. Context

Addressing a gap in European biotechnology, IBISBA's mission is to provide world-class cutting-edge research and innovation services enabling the development of biotechnology as a technology cornerstone of the circular bioeconomy. To achieve this, IBISBA integrates Europe's leading public-operated research infrastructure facilities into a coordinated business environment.

From a science and technology standpoint IBISBA aims to develop new science concepts, tools, and methodologies to underpin the production of modular, interoperable services that are interlinked in workflows to support the seamless development of bioprocesses.

In the framework of the H2020 project IBISBA 1.0, IBISBA member facilities have experimented the production of R&D services mainly through the TransNationalAccess (TNA) programme. So far, through TNA IBISBA has produced services to support R&D projects proposed by users, employing one or more facilities to reach specific project aims.

As part of the overall IBISBA infrastructure, IBISBAHub¹ is a web-based registry that supports data management and any information related to the projects carried out by IBISBA. The IBISBAHub is a configured and extended instance of the widely used FAIRDOM-SEEK software². FAIRDOM-SEEK (and thus IBISBAHub) structures a project into Investigations which contain Studies, which in turn contain Assays. This is a modified version of the ISA structure³.

It is mandated that all TNA projects and their processes and outcomes are registered on IBISBAHub. The data that is registered on IBISBAHub may be private and specific to a project or user, or it may be shared, for example common protocols. The data may be stored on IBISBAHub or kept elsewhere (for example at a facility) with the access reference being recorded in the IBISBAHub. The confidentiality of all information is ensured by IBISBAHub's extensive security options.

IBISBAHub has the capability to read a spreadsheet⁴ detailing the steps⁵ that will be carried out as part of a project. This spreadsheet import allows the quick design and description within IBISBAHub of an IBISBA project. It is important to note that the details of each step, its timing and the input and output data of the project must currently be entered or uploaded manually, using IBISBAHub's user interface.

The process of carrying out an IBISBA project can be complex as it may involve multiple facilities or partners; it can be considered as a "business process". The work described in this document examines the possibility of generating a business process model (BPM) for an IBISBA project and loading it into a BPM system that then supports the enactment of the IBISBA project. BPM systems support the concept of participants in a project - corresponding to the IBISBA facilities.

¹ <https://hub.ibisba.eu>

² <https://fair-dom.org/platform/seek/>

³ <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/>

⁴ This spreadsheet is compatible with the output of WP6's TasCu system <https://tascu.vtt.fi/tascu>

⁵ The steps may be assigned to specific people or to institutions.

For IBISBA, we considered a selection of BPM systems and finally selected Flowable⁶. The Flowable BPM system was set up and installed on a virtual machine in the same overall infrastructure at INRAE as IBISBAHub. The loading of a project into the BPM system is done as a manual step, as is the starting of the project within the BPM system. The communication with the assignees of the work, and the updating of the IBISBAHub is done⁷ automatically by the BPM system. The BPM system thus removes the need for manual updating of IBISBAHub.

Throughout this document, the term IBISBAHub is used. In practice, the work was carried out on a specially modified demonstrator version of IBISBAHub, rather than the main IBISBAHub itself⁸.

2. Introduction

Business Process Models (BPMs) are workflows⁹ operating at a relatively coarse-grained meta-workflow level. BPMs enable coordination between computational workflows and manual steps using event mechanisms and incorporating business rules. BPMs are now well established with an established execution language and graphical notation (BPMN). BPMs, however, are complex to make and normally aimed at experts to develop on behalf of users to run. A number of commercial enterprises (Oracle, Microsoft, IBM) and open source BPM systems (Activiti, Bonitasoft, Camunda, jBPM, FloSuite, ProcessMaker) are available.

The possible use of BPM for Synthetic Biology holds great potential, especially in the case of coordinating projects that run on distributed facilities.

Deliverable 7.4 evaluates an open source Business Process Model system to model and help enact a project of IBISBA work. The task includes the creation of a demonstrator for a complete project. The enacted workflows and their associated research objects are accessible from the IBISBAHub.

Details of the implementation are given in Annex B: Architecture and implementation. The main body of this document describes the overall approach and lessons learnt.

The major lesson learnt from this piece of work is that **in any future BPM-related developments in IBISBA, the BPM requirements must primarily consider the facilities and their work allocation. The detailed steps are a secondary (possibly minor) consideration.**

⁶ Flowable is distributed under the Apache V2 license. The Apache License is a permissive free software license written by the Apache Software Foundation (ASF)

⁷ This uses IBISBAHub's REST API <https://docs.seek4science.org/help/user-guide/api.html>

⁸ The demonstrator IBISBAHub runs on a different virtual machine but in the same overall infrastructure at INRAE as IBISBAHub itself

⁹ A distinction is made between (a) “workflows” that describe the overall flow of work that occurs within a project, and (b) “computational workflows” that are executed as single stages and call programs to enact a step.

Terminology

The term **step** is used to indicate a Project, Investigation, Study or Assay. A project corresponds to a piece of work carried out by IBISBA. The Investigation, Study and Assay follow an adapted version of the ISA structure.¹⁰

- A Project is a step that has sub-steps for each of its Investigations. It is not part of another step.
- An Investigation is a step that is part of a Project step and has sub-steps for each of its Studies
- A Study is a step that is part of an Investigation step and has sub-steps for each of its Assays.
- An Assay is a step that is part of a Study step. It does not have any sub-steps.

Scope Assessment

The scope of the demonstrator system was clearly defined at the beginning of the work. Several importance scoping decisions were made:

- The work is a demonstrator system.
 - It is intended to show **what is possible** and to **identify problems**
 - Releases of IBISBAHub include extensive time on the development of the user interface. The interface of the demonstrator will show that the information can be presented. Information is **not presented in a user-friendly manner**.
- The demonstrator does not include capabilities that should be present in a production-ready system. These capabilities would be possible in a BPM system.
 - The project that is being enacted **cannot be dynamically changed**
 - The enactment does **not include error recovery nor error propagation**

The project must be well-defined. The BPM system allows re-ordering and parallelization of steps. The demonstrator assumes that **data must be produced before it is consumed**.

Selection of BPM System

The authors, together with Nicky Chan, a student at the University of Manchester, evaluated a number of BPM systems¹¹:

- jBPM - <https://www.jbpm.org/> - a RedHat (<https://www.redhat.com>) sponsored BPM system
- Activiti - <http://www.activiti.org/> - produced by developers who worked on jBPM but “clean” source code
- Camunda BPM <https://camunda.com/> – which is developed from a fork of Activiti
- Flowable - <http://www.flowable.org/> - which is developed from forks of Activiti 5 and 6

¹⁰ <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/>

¹¹ They also examined (and rejected) the possibility of using If This Then That (IFTTT)

As may be seen from the summary above, all of the BPM systems evaluated share a common heritage from jBPM, and two are developed from forks of Activiti.

jBPM itself implements the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) 2.0 standard - <https://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/>

BPMN is “the de-facto standard for business processes diagrams. It is intended to be used directly by the stakeholders who design, manage and realize business processes, but at the same time be precise enough to allow BPMN diagrams to be translated into software process components. BPMN has an easy-to-use flowchart-like notation that is independent of any particular implementation environment.”

Owing to their common heritage, and the functionality required to support BPMN, the systems are very similar. An extensive comparison is given in the Annexes. The authors chose flowable based upon its support, tutorials and configurability. This choice though would need to be revisited in any future use of BPM systems in IBISBA.

Demonstration

Implementation was demonstrated using a modified version of "An inventory of the *Aspergillus niger* secretome by combining in silico predictions with shotgun proteomics data" from IBISBAHub¹²

Figure 1 Demonstration project

¹² <https://hub.ibisba.eu/projects/14>

It should be noted that the majority of the steps in the project are assigned to “Alan Williams”. The study “Validation of the secretome of *Aspergillus niger*” and the assay “Mass Spectrometry Analysis” are assigned to “Munazah Andrabi”

The result of enacting the project is available in a summary table:

BPMN report for Project <i>Aspergillus niger</i> secretome at 2021-07-08T08:43:36+00:00					
Type	Title	Assignee	Status	Started	Finished
Project	Aspergillus niger secretome	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 13:45:04 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:25 UTC
Investigation	In-silico prediction and mass spectro...	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 13:50:49 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:21 UTC
Study	In-Silico Prediction	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 13:56:59 UTC	2021-07-07 14:04:25 UTC
Assay	Obtain proteomes	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:02:34 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:00 UTC
Assay	Signal Peptide Predictions	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:03:23 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:38 UTC
Assay	Orthology identification	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:03:49 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:55 UTC
Assay	GPI Anchor Predictions	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:04:17 UTC	2021-07-07 14:04:21 UTC
Study	Culture experiments	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:04:31 UTC	2021-07-08 08:19:22 UTC
Assay	Growth experiment	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:04:37 UTC	2021-07-07 19:23:43 UTC
Assay	Liquid chromatography tandem mass spe...	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-08 08:11:27 UTC	2021-07-08 08:19:16 UTC
Study	Validation of the secretome of Asperg...	Munazah Andrabi	completed	2021-07-08 08:42:09 UTC	2021-07-08 08:42:52 UTC
Assay	Mass Spectrometry Analysis	Munazah Andrabi	completed	2021-07-08 08:38:16 UTC	2021-07-08 08:38:23 UTC
Study	Metabolic model analysis	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-08 08:42:57 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:18 UTC
Assay	Obtain metabolic model	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-08 08:43:02 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:08 UTC
Assay	Identify enzymes from spectra	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-08 08:43:11 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:14 UTC

Figure 2 Completed project

3. Recommendations

This section contains the authors' recommendations for future work within IBISBA. The recommendations were discovered or highlighted during the BPM work. They are not specific to BPMs.

1. Much useful information about project enactment was expected to be gathered as part of the TNAs within IBISBA 1.0. However, this has not happened, because early rounds of TNA were unprepared for this. IBISBA must rapidly perform a post-analysis of previously enacted TNAs, and enforce information gathering for current TNAs.
2. IBISBA should evaluate a selection of facilities for information on how they track a project internally, how they expose data, how they transfer control and/or data to other facilities and how and when they report to a customer.
3. IBISBA must be concerned with how data is exposed by facilities. It may not be feasible to transfer data to IBISBAHub, or, indeed between facilities. The IBISBA consortium may find it necessary to enforce rules for how information is exposed by facilities.
4. IBISBA must assume that the facilities are fully capable of carrying out their parts of a project. IBISBA should concentrate on what actually happens when a facility, or multiple facilities carry out a project for a customer. IBISBAHub must not be concerned with individual steps that are internal to a facility.
5. Describing planned projects on IBISBAHub is a useful feature and must be supported. The granularity and features of such plans must be defined after examination of actual projects.
6. IBISBA should be concerned with making it as simple as possible for facilities to update IBISBAHub with information about what is done at the facility. This will require changes to IBISBAHub's REST API.
7. If a project is multi-facility then IBISBA should be concerned about how to ensure handover of necessary data or control. This may include file type and format checking within the IBISBA infrastructure.
8. A BPM system will be useful for IBISBA when coordinating multi-facility projects. The BPM model will include activities corresponding to the pieces of work carried out by each facility.
9. A project report is a useful feature. Its accuracy will depend upon how updates from a facility happen. The reporting of a project's status must be included within IBISBAHub.

4. Lessons learnt

Granularity of Enactment

The current demonstrator acts as the enactment system for each of the steps in the project. Although this works, it assumes that the facility (or facilities) performing the project do not have their own internal enactment systems, or are prepared to run what is, in effect, a dual enactment systems. This is unlikely to be true in practice.

If we examine the project, we see that it consists of three pieces of work:

1. The studies “In-Silico Prediction” and “Culture experiments” performed by “Alan Williams”
2. The study “Validation of the secretome of *Aspergillus niger*” performed by “Munazah Andrabi”
3. The last study “Metabolic model analysis” performed by “Alan Williams”

Single Facility Interpretation

If all the work is carried out at a single facility (and the different assignees are only specified as “useful information”), then it is unlikely that the facility’s enactment system would constantly update the IBISBAHub.

The enactment would in effect be a single full registration of a project on the Hub. No information would be available on the Hub until the project was completed.

Sub-contracting Facility Interpretation

If the main facility where “Alan Williams” works, subcontracts the single study to a separate facility where “Munazah Andrabi” works, then it is probable that the main facility has its own mechanisms for dealing with sub-contractors. So far as the Hub is concerned, this is the same as the project running on the single main facility.

Multi-facility Interpretation

If the project is enacted on two separate facilities (A and M), then it is reasonable for a BPM system to enact the overall project. However, there would, in this case, only be three pieces of work, or in the terminology used in this document, three steps.

1. Facility A is notified of the project start. When the first two studies are complete, the value for “Proteins detected” is registered on the Hub.
2. Facility M is notified that it can start work, and where the “Proteins detected” data can be found. When facility M has completed its work, the enactment proceeds to
3. Facility A is notified that they can resume work. When they have finished, the overall project is updated on the Hub.

Granularity Summary

The work carried out by a BPM system tied to IBISBAHub, strongly depends upon the facility allocation of the work. In practice, it is very unlikely to depend upon the detailed steps of the work. For this reason, in any future BPM-related developments in IBISBA, **the BPM requirements must primarily consider the facilities and their work allocation.**

Documentation

IBISBAHub currently supports the association of documentation with an Assay. This work showed the need to also associate documentation with Investigations, Studies, and the Project itself. This requirement has been registered as a GitHub issue for IBISBAHub (and for FAIRDOM-SEEK).

Forms

The forms auto-generated in the BPM system are relatively primitive - certainly in comparison to Google Forms. It is anticipated that in a production system, an alternative form system would be used. Flowable's API appears to support this. The system could be an existing one, such as Google Forms, leverage IBISBAHub (or similar) possibly using the serendipity¹³ system.

Extension of BPM Activity

The current demonstrator uses explicit Start and Finish Sentry activities. These are called within the BPM as part of the overall model before and after each step. It is possible within BPM systems to, instead, extend an activity class. It is proposed that, in any future development of BPM in IBISBA, the activity for a step will be extended with code that mimics the current Sentries.

This extension would greatly simplify the model for a project. It is possible that it would also aid in any facility-aware IBISBA BPM work.

5. Partners involved in the work

UNIMAN: Alan Williams, Carole Goble, Munazah Andrabi

WUR: Jasper Koehorst.

KNIME: Stefan Helfrich

¹³ <https://github.com/Robinyo/serendipity/tree/master/projects/flowable>

6. Annexes

a. Annex A: Comparison of BPM Systems

The following comparison is a “best effort” and no guarantee is given as to its correctness. The comparison will not be up-to-date. For recent information, readers are recommended to visit the BPM systems’ websites.

Workflow Features	jBPM	Activiti	Camunda BPM	Flowable
There is the concept of states (start and stop) and tasks	Green	Green	Green	Green
Can move to the next task/state once the current task has finished	Green	Green	Green	Green
Can alter the workflow depending on the result from a task	Green	Green	Green	Green
Time - Should be able to execute a task after a certain amount of time has elapsed	Green	Green	Green	Green
Tasks can invoke remote systems and get the result after the interaction through notifications	Green	Green	Green	Green
Timeouts - should be able to alter the workflow if a remote system does not respond	Green	Green	Green	Green
Workflows are configurable	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Yellow
Workflows can be started	Green	Green	Green	Green
Workflows can be cancelled	Green	Green	Green	Green
Point of no return - once past this point in the workflow, cancel requests are denied	Green	Green	Green	Green
Notifications can be sent once a task/process has completed	Green	Green	Green	Green

Workflow System Features	jBPM	Activiti	Camunda BPM	Flowable
Spring Boot integration	Yellow	Green	Green	Green
The workflow system should be able to identify different customers	Green	Green	Green	Green
There should be a concept of orders which contains a unique order number	Green	Green	Green	Green
Each customer has a list of products which they can order (may not be the same for every customer)	Green	Green	Green	Green
The status of an order can be updated through notifications (e.g. from remote systems or from the completion of a task)	Green	Green	Green	Green
The workflow invoked should depend on both the customer and the product ordered	Green	Green	Green	Green
The system should be able to accept orders in a JSON format	Green	Green	Green	Green
The progress of orders can be viewed	Green	Green	Green	Green
More than one workflow can be started at the same time	Green	Green	Green	Green

Non-functional properties	jBPM	Activiti	Camunda BPM	Flowable
Tutorial	Red	Red	Yellow	Green
Documentation: Spring Boot integration	Red	Red	Yellow	Green
Documentation: workflow features	Green	Red	Green	Green
Still being developed?	Green	Green	Green	Green
Forum for questions?	Yellow	Green	Green	Green

The authors chose Flowable based upon its support, tutorials and configurability.

b. Annex B: Architecture and Implementation

Overall Architecture

There were several questions that initially arose for this piece of work:

- Whether there needs to be a separate BPM system?
- When should the project running on the BPM be registered on the Hub?
- When should the Hub be updated with project status?

Is there a Need for a separate BPM System?

The possibility was considered that this work could be done by extensions to IBISBAHub.

IBISBAHub already has the capability to store a description of a project. This is not limited to a completed project, but can include planned projects or those in progress. In addition, IBISBAHub can specify much of the information needed for the enactment of a project, such as the associated people or infrastructures.

There are two main arguments against such extensions

- Separation of concerns - IBISBAHub has an intended purpose and capability. It should not be extended out of this area without good reason. In addition, such extension should be done without unduly affecting the current functionality.
- No reinvention - IBISBAHub cooperates with existing software and systems. It does not duplicate capabilities that exist elsewhere. Examples of this are:
 - The use of ELIXIR AAI through OmniAuth for user authentication
 - JWSONline and Copasi for model simulation
 - Publishing into Zenodo
 - DOI generation with DataCite

To prevent reinvention, IBISBAHub should cooperate with an existing BPM system. We should use an existing BPM system and add integration capabilities to the Hub.

Registration of the Project

The stage at which an enacted project appears on IBISBAHub was discussed. There are two main possibilities:

- A BPM project is generated from a distinct project plan. That plan is not registered on IBISBAHub. Instead the enactment of the BPM project includes the registration and description of the corresponding project on IBISBAHub. This possibility could have used the spreadsheet generated from, for example, TasCu
- The project is registered and planned on IBISBAHub. The BPM project is then generated from a project on IBISBAHub.

The second option was chosen as it involves a lesser amount of possible confusion, and makes the planned project accessible in a way known to IBISBA users. The first would entail learning the spreadsheet format and the BPM system's project description.

Updating of IBISBAHub

The frequency with which the project information is updated on IBISBAHub was considered. There is a simple option of not updating until the BPM project has been finished / cancelled. This was considered unreasonable as the IBISBAHub is a natural place for people to look for information about a project. Instead, the IBISBAHub is updated with information from the BPM system as soon as that information is available.

MoSCoW Assessment

As part of the design of the demonstrator system, a Must have, Should have, Could have, Won't have (MoSCoW) assessment was carried out of its requirements; the individual requirements were assigned to be implemented on the IBISBAHub or within the BPM system.

Must have on IBISBAHub

- Assignment of steps to specific users
- Data placeholders
- Ability to satisfy the placeholders with actual data
- Production of a BPM for a project

Must have in the BPM System

- Notifications about a step based on user assignments
 - Specifies the inputs for the step
 - Specifies how to state that the step is finished and
 - How to state the outputs of the step
- User information about
 - Open tasks - (a task is the enactment of a step)
 - Their assigned tasks
 - Tasks assigned to their facility

Should have in the BPM System

- A track of events with timeline and user information
- A dashboard of tasks that are open for a BPM user

Could have in the BPM System

- Synchronisation with the Hub during process enactment
- State visualisation

Extensions to IBISBAHub

As described in *Overall Architecture*, it was decided that the use of a BPM's capabilities would not overly affect IBISBAHub. However, there are a few areas where extensions were implemented to aid in this work.

Specification of Assignee

If BPMN support is enabled on IBISBAHub, then a step (project, investigation, study or assay) can be **assigned** to a person. *For the demonstrator, that person must be registered on IBISBAHub.*

Status

In order for a user to understand the state of the enactment of a project, the concept of a **status** for a step (project, investigation, study or assay) was introduced. This allows IBISBAHub to show that a step is *planned, running, completed, cancelled or failed*. In the demonstrator, only *planned, running and completed* are supported.

Placeholders

When a project is planned, there may be data whose value is already known; whatever happens during the project enactment, that data is fixed. However, there is also data where the value is determined when the project is enacted. For example, the "proteins detected" by mass spectrometry are then subject to mass spectrometry analysis.

The concept of "proteins detected" by mass spectrometry is not actual data when the project is planned. Instead, it is considered as a **placeholder**. When the project is enacted, once mass spectrometry is complete, then actual data will 'fill in' the placeholder. That actual data will then be an input to mass spectrometry analysis (rather than the placeholder).

Start and Finish Times

Although IBISBAHub have the start and finish dates for a Project, it was determined that this was insufficient accuracy for a project's enactment. For this reason, IBISBAHub was extended to allow the start and finish date and time for each step. This allows the accurate tracking and provenance for a project's enactment.

BPMN Export

Figure 3 BPMN extensions

IBISBAHub was extended to support the generation of a BPMN model for a Project. This is described in *Draft BPMN Model Generation*

BPMN Report

IBISBAHub has been extended to show a summary table of the BPM's enactment of a Project.

It must be noted that this summary table is very much a draft. Any such table would need extensive revision for a production system.

Implementation

The overall enactment implementation can be visualized as:

Figure 4 Overall Implementation

The solid and dotted arrows happen once for a project enactment. The dashed arrows happen **two times per step** (once at the start of the step, and once at its finish).

For the demonstration, we used a simplified version of "An inventory of the *Aspergillus niger* secretome by combining in silico predictions with shotgun proteomics data" from IBISBAHub¹⁴.

¹⁴ <https://hub.ibisba.eu/projects/14>

Project Creation

The project was created manually. A description of the project's structure was then read from a spreadsheet and used to populate the project.

Project was successfully updated.

Aspergillus niger secretome

Dashboard

The ecological niche occupied by a fungal species, its pathogenicity and its usefulness as a microbial cell factory to a large degree depends on its secretome. Protein secretion usually requires the presence of a N-terminal signal peptide (SP) and by scanning for this feature using available highly accurate SP-prediction tools, the fraction of potentially secreted proteins can be directly predicted.

However, prediction of a SP does not guarantee that the protein is actually secreted and current in silico prediction methods suffer from gene-model errors introduced during genome annotation. We were able to improve the in silico inventory of *A. niger* secretory proteins by combining different gene-model predictions from neighbouring *Aspergilli* and thereby avoiding prediction conflicts associated with inaccurate gene-models. The expected accuracy of signal peptide prediction for proteins that lack homologous sequences in the proteomes of related species is 85%. An experimental validation of the predicted proteome confirmed in silico predictions.

<p>SEEK ID: http://parts.ibisba.eu/projects/4</p> <p>Public web page: Not specified</p> <p>Internal web page: Not specified</p> <p>Organisms: aspergillus niger</p> <p>Status: planned</p> <p>Assignee: Alan Williams</p>	<p>FAIRDOM PALs: No PALs for this Project</p> <p>Project administrators: Alan Williams, Munazah Andrabi</p> <p>Asset housekeepers: No Asset housekeepers for this Project</p> <p>Asset gatekeepers: No Asset gatekeepers for this Project</p> <p>Project created: 6th Jul 2021</p>
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Figure 5 Project registered on the Hub

Selected: [Aspergillus niger secretome](#) (Project)

Description: The ecological niche occupied by a fungal species, its pathogenicity and its usefulness as a microbial cell factory to...

SEEK ID: <http://parts.ibisba.eu/projects/4>

Aspergillus niger secretome

- In-silico prediction and mass spectrometric validation of the Aspergillus niger secretome
 - In-Silico Prediction
 - Obtain proteomes
 - Signal Peptide Predictions
 - Orthology identification
 - GPI Anchor Predictions
 - Culture experiments
 - Growth experiment
 - Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry
 - Proteins detected
 - Validation of the secretome of Aspergillus niger
 - Mass Spectrometry Analysis
 - Proteins detected
 - Metabolic model analysis
 - Obtain metabolic model
 - Identify enzymes from spectra

Figure 6 Overview of the Aspergillus Project

As may be seen the structure of the project is relatively simple with just one investigation. That investigation contains four studies with one or more assays each.

One important aspect of the project to note is that “Proteins detected” is produced by “Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry” and consumed by “Mass Spectrometry Analysis”.

Draft BPMN Model Generation

A BPMN model may be generated for a Project from the “Generate BPMN” Action when viewing the Project.

Figure 7 Generation of draft BPM model

Draft BPMN Model

The BPMN model is an XML document that conforms to <https://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN>. A concise extract of the BPMN for the Aspergillus project is:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<definitions ...>
  <process id="11740397-1785-4d81-a091-ebbd8bbe19a6"
name="aspergillus_niger_secretome_model" isExecutable="true">
  <startEvent id="project-4-start" />
    <!-- Start Sentry for Project "Aspergillus niger secretome" -->
    <callActivity id="project-4-start-sentry" name="Aspergillus niger secretome Start Sentry"
calledElement="pisastartsentry" ... />
    <sequenceFlow sourceRef="project-4-start" targetRef="project-4-start-sentry" id="project-4-start-to-
project-4-start-sentry" />
    <subProcess id="investigation-1" name="In-silico prediction and mass spectrometric validation of the
Aspergillus niger secretome">
      <startEvent id="investigation-1-start" />
```

```

<!-- Start Sentry for Investigation "In-silico prediction..." -->
<callActivity id="investigation-1-start-sentry" name="In-silico prediction and mass spectrometric
validation of the Aspergillus niger secretome Start Sentry" calledElement="pisastartsentry" ... />
  <sequenceFlow sourceRef="investigation-1-start" targetRef="investigation-1-start-sentry"
id="investigation-1-start-to-investigation-1-start-sentry" />
  <subProcess id="study-1" name="In-Silico Prediction">
    <startEvent id="study-1-start" />
    <!-- Start Sentry for Study "In-silico Prediction..." -->
    <callActivity id="study-1-start-sentry" name="In-Silico Prediction Start Sentry"
calledElement="pisastartsentry" ... />
      <sequenceFlow sourceRef="study-1-start" targetRef="study-1-start-sentry" id="study-1-start-to-
study-1-start-sentry" />
      <subProcess id="assay-1" name="Obtain proteomes">
        <startEvent id="assay-1-start" />
        <!-- Start Sentry for Assay "Obtain proteome" -->
        <callActivity id="assay-1-start-sentry" name="Obtain proteomes Start Sentry"
calledElement="pisastartsentry" ... />
          <sequenceFlow sourceRef="assay-1-start" targetRef="assay-1-start-sentry" id="assay-1-start-to-
assay-1-start-sentry" />
          <!-- Finish Sentry for Assay "Obtain proteome" -->
          <callActivity id="assay-1-finish-sentry" name="Obtain proteomes Finish Sentry"
calledElement="pisafinishsentry" ... />
            <sequenceFlow sourceRef="assay-1-start-sentry" targetRef="assay-1-finish-sentry" id="assay-1-
start-sentry-to-assay-1-finish-sentry" />
            <endEvent id="assay-1-end" />
            <sequenceFlow sourceRef="assay-1-finish-sentry" targetRef="assay-1-end" id="assay-1-finish-
sentry-to-assay-1-end" />
          </subProcess>
        ...
      <!-- Finish Sentry for Study "In-silico Prediction..." -->
      <callActivity id="study-1-finish-sentry" name="In-Silico Prediction Finish Sentry"
calledElement="pisafinishsentry" ... />
        <endEvent id="study-1-end" />
        <!-- Finish Sentry for Investigation "In-silico prediction..." -->
        <callActivity id="investigation-1-finish-sentry" name="In-silico prediction and mass
spectrometric validation of the Aspergillus niger secretome Finish Sentry"
calledElement="pisafinishsentry" ... />
          <endEvent id="study-1-end" />
        </subProcess>
      </subProcess>
    <!-- Finish Sentry for Project "Aspergillus niger secretome" -->
  
```

```
<callActivity id="project-4-finish-sentry" name="Aspergillus niger secretome Finish Sentry"
calledElement="pisafinishsentry" ... />
<sequenceFlow sourceRef="investigation-1" targetRef="project-4-finish-sentry" id="investigation-1-
to-project-4-finish-sentry" />
<endEvent id="project-4-end" />
<sequenceFlow sourceRef="project-4-finish-sentry" targetRef="project-4-end" id="project-4-finish-
sentry-to-project-4-end" />
</process>
</definitions>
```

Figure 8 Draft BPM model

The callActivities highlighted in **blue** correspond to the **dashed** arrows in Figure 4 Overall Implementation. The callActivities (termed Sentries) are called at the start and finish of each step.

Because the steps are nested inside one another, the call structure is:

- Overall project start sentry
- For each investigation in the project
 - Investigation start sentry
 - For each study in the investigation
 - Study start sentry
 - For each assay in the study
 - Assay start sentry
 - Performing of assay
 - Assay finish sentry
 - Study finish sentry
 - Investigation finish sentry
- Overall project finish sentry

An explanation of the functionality of the sentries is given below.

Loading the BPM

The BPM model is loaded into the BPM system. **This is a manual step.** The BPM model may be modified within the BPM system. A BPM application is generated corresponding to the, possibly modified, BPM model.

Start the BPM

The BPM application may be started within the BPM system.

Figure 9 Start BPM Application

Once the BPM application has been started a summary report may be viewed within the Hub.

BPMN report for Project Aspergillus niger secretome at 2021-07-10T18:16:09+00:00

Type	Title	Assignee	Status	Started	Finished
Project	Aspergillus niger secretome	Alan Williams	planned		
Investigation	In-silico prediction and mass spectro...	Alan Williams	planned		
Study	In-Silico Prediction	Alan Williams	planned		
Assay	Obtain proteomes	Alan Williams	planned		
Assay	Signal Peptide Predictions	Alan Williams	planned		
Assay	Orthology Identification	Alan Williams	planned		
Assay	GPI Anchor Predictions	Alan Williams	planned		
Study	Culture experiments	Alan Williams	planned		
Assay	Growth experiment	Alan Williams	planned		
Assay	Liquid chromatography tandem mass spe...	Alan Williams	planned		
Study	Validation of the secretome of Asperg...	Munazah Andrabi	planned		
Assay	Mass Spectrometry Analysis	Munazah Andrabi	planned		
Study	Metabolic model analysis	Alan Williams	planned		
Assay	Obtain metabolic model	Alan Williams	planned		
Assay	Identify enzymes from spectra	Alan Williams	planned		

Figure 10 Initial Summary Report

The summary report will initially state that all the steps of the project are planned. When the assignee of the project indicates that it has started, the first line of the table will be updated.

The Start Sentry

A start sentry is enacted at the beginning of every step.

Figure 11 Start Sentry

Step 1: E-mails a notification to the assignee for the step. For example

Figure 12 Start Sentry Notification

Step 2a: Presents a form for the assignee. For all steps, the form allows the addition of documentation about the step. If placeholders must be satisfied, the start form contains fields for the entry of those placeholders. The satisfaction of those placeholders is mandatory in the form.

Study In-Silico Prediction is ready to start

Description (if available)

A majority rule based classifier that evaluates signal peptide (SP) predictions from the best homologs of three neighbouring *Aspergillus* species was developed to create an improved list of potential signal peptide containing proteins encoded by the *Aspergillus niger* genome.

Starter notes

Notes

in-silico-start.txt
Added by Admin , Today at 2:54 PM

Figure 13 Start Sentry Form

Step 2b: In addition, when the step is an Assay, the form shows the Assay's protocol (if any) and links to the inputs of the Assay (if any). For example,

Assay Mass Spectrometry Analysis is ready to start

Description (if available)

Description withheld

Protocol (if available)

No protocol

Starter notes

Notes

Drop or [Select a file](#)

Inputs

[Proteins detected](#)

Figure 14 Start Sentry Form for Assay

In this case the step for the *Mass Spectrometry Analysis* takes the *Proteins detected* as input, as indicated in Figure 6 Overview of the Aspergillus Project

Step 3: The start sentry then updates the Hub with the information from the form

- a. The step is changed to running
- b. Notes (if any) will be associated with the step

For example, the study notes *in-silico-start.txt* are uploaded to the Hub.

The screenshot shows a document page in the Hub. At the top left is a document icon. The title is "studies 1 Notes" followed by "Version 1". Below the title is a grey bar with the text "No description specified". The main content area contains the following information: "SEEK ID: <http://parts.ibisba.eu/documents/1?version=1>", "Filename: notes" with a magnifying glass and download icon, "Format: Plain text document", and "Size: 55 Bytes". Below this is a grey bar with "Selected: studies 1 Notes (Document)", "Description: No description", and "SEEK ID: <http://parts.ibisba.eu/documents/1>". At the bottom, there is a light blue bar with a document icon and the text "studies 1 Notes".

```
This is a report on the start of In silico Prediction
```

Figure 15 Notes uploaded to the Hub

The running state can be observed in the updated status report

BPMN report for Project Aspergillus niger secretome at 2021-07-07T14:04:43+00:00

Type	Title	Assignee	Status	Started	Finished
Project	Aspergillus niger secretome	Alan Williams	running	2021-07-07 13:45:04 UTC	
Investigation	In-silico prediction and mass spectro...	Alan Williams	running	2021-07-07 13:50:49 UTC	
Study	In-Silico Prediction	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 13:56:59 UTC	2021-07-07 14:04:25 UTC
Assay	Obtain proteomes	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:02:34 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:00 UTC
Assay	Signal Peptide Predictions	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:03:23 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:38 UTC
Assay	Orthology Identification	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:03:49 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:55 UTC
Assay	GPI Anchor Predictions	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:04:17 UTC	2021-07-07 14:04:21 UTC
Study	Culture experiments	Alan Williams	running	2021-07-07 14:04:31 UTC	
Assay	Growth experiment	Alan Williams	running	2021-07-07 14:04:37 UTC	
Assay	Liquid chromatography tandem mass spe...	Alan Williams	planned		
Study	Validation of the secretome of Asperg...	Munazah Andrabi	planned		
Assay	Mass Spectrometry Analysis	Munazah Andrabi	planned		
Study	Metabolic model analysis	Alan Williams	planned		

Figure 16 Updated status report

The Finish Sentry

A finish sentry is enacted at the end of every step. Its structure is very similar to that of the start sentry.

Figure 17 Finish Sentry

Step 1: E-mails a notification to the assignee for the step. For example

Assay Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry can be finished

Please visit the form at <http://dev.ibisba.eu/flowable-ui/workflow/#/tasks> to finish it

Figure 18 Finish Sentry Notification

Step 2a: Presents a form for the assignee. For all steps, the form allows the addition of documentation about what happened during the running of the step.

Step 2b: If the step corresponds to an Assay that has outputs, the form contains a field for each output.

Assay Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry can be finished

Finish report

Report

Drop or

Outputs

Proteins detected

Drop or

Figure 19 Finish Sentry Form for Assay

In this case, the step *Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry* has a single output, *Proteins detected*. In the initial Project on the Hub, this is a placeholder. When it is satisfied, the value can then be used as the input to *Mass Spectrometry Analysis* as indicated in Figure 14 Start Sentry Form for Assay

Step 3: The finish sentry then updates the Hub with the information from the form

- a. The step is changed to completed
- b. Notes (if any) will be associated with the step
- c. Any outputs from an assay will be:
 - i. Registered on the Hub
 - ii. Indicated as satisfying the placeholder

Selected: Actual protein results (Data file) Tree Split Graph

Description: No description Fullscreen

SEEK ID: http://parts.ibisba.eu/data_files/3

- In-silico prediction and mass spectrometric validation of the Aspergillus niger secretome
 - In-Silico Prediction
 - Culture experiments
 - Growth experiment
 - Liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry
 - Actual protein results
 - Proteins detected
 - Validation of the secretome of Aspergillus niger
 - Mass Spectrometry Analysis**
 - Actual protein results
 - Proteins detected
 - Metabolic model analysis
 - Obtain metabolic model
 - Identify enzymes from spectra

Figure 20 Proteins detected placeholder satisfied

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	# Proteins										
2											
3	No.	Functional group	Description		Locus tag	SignalP3	SP accordi	Spectr	Spectr	Spectr	MEROPS
4	1	CARBOHYDRATE	endo-14-xylanase xynB - Aspergillus niger		An01g00780	SP	yes	0	0	12	
5	2	ACTIVE	strong similarity to alphaalpha-trehalase treA - Aspergillus nidulans		An01g01540	SP	likely SP	10	10	0	
6	3	ENZYMES	strong similarity to 13-beta-glucanosyltransferase gel1 - Aspergillus fun		An01g03090	SP	likely SP	1	0	1	
7	4		strong similarity to mixed-linked glucanase precursor MLG1 - Cochlob		An01g04560	SP	likely SP	0	0	4	
8	5		strong similarity to alpha-L-rhamnosidase A precursor rhaA - Aspergillu		An01g06620	SP	yes	0	7	0	
9	6		xylosidase xinD - Aspergillus niger-		An01g09960	SP	yes	5	23	100	
10	7		strong similarity to enzyme with sugar transferase activity from patent J		An01g10930	SP	yes	3	4	1	
11	8		14-beta-D-glucan cellobiohydrolase B precursor cbhB - Aspergillus nig		An01g11660	SP	yes	1	0	1	
12	9		strong similarity to hypothetical glucan beta-13 exoglucanase exgS - A		An01g12450	SP	yes	16	12	10	
13	10		strong similarity to mannosyl-oligosaccharide 12-alpha-mannosidase m		An01g12550	SP	yes	95	71	13	
14	11		alpha-galactosidase agIB - Aspergillus niger-		An02g11150	SP	yes	25	7	2	
15	12		strong similarity to diglycosidase related protein SEQ ID NO:10 from p		An03g00500	SP	yes	16	15	15	
16	13		endo-14-beta-xylanase A precursor xynA - Aspergillus niger [putative s		An03g00940	SP	yes	0	0	2	
17	14		14-beta-D-arabinoxylan arabinofuranohydrotase axhA - Aspergillus nig		An03g00960	SP	likely SP	1	0	6	
18	15		similarity to endo-beta-14-glucanase - Bacillus polymyxa		An03g01050	SP	yes	1	0	0	

Figure 21 Uploaded proteins

Project Finish

The project is finished when the Finish Sentry for the project step has been enacted i.e. the project's assignee indicates it is finished, any report is uploaded and the status of the project is changed to completed.

BPMN report for Project Aspergillus niger secretome at 2021-07-08T08:43:36+00:00

Type	Title	Assignee	Status	Started	Finished
Project	Aspergillus niger secretome	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 13:45:04 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:25 UTC
Investigation	In-silico prediction and mass spectro...	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 13:50:49 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:21 UTC
Study	In-Silico Prediction	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 13:56:59 UTC	2021-07-07 14:04:25 UTC
Assay	Obtain proteomes	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:02:34 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:00 UTC
Assay	Signal Peptide Predictions	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:03:23 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:38 UTC
Assay	Orthology identification	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:03:49 UTC	2021-07-07 14:03:55 UTC
Assay	GPI Anchor Predictions	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:04:17 UTC	2021-07-07 14:04:21 UTC
Study	Culture experiments	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:04:31 UTC	2021-07-08 08:19:22 UTC
Assay	Growth experiment	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-07 14:04:37 UTC	2021-07-07 19:23:43 UTC
Assay	Liquid chromatography tandem mass spe...	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-08 08:11:27 UTC	2021-07-08 08:19:16 UTC
Study	Validation of the secretome of Asperg...	Munazah Andrabi	completed	2021-07-08 08:42:09 UTC	2021-07-08 08:42:52 UTC
Assay	Mass Spectrometry Analysis	Munazah Andrabi	completed	2021-07-08 08:38:16 UTC	2021-07-08 08:38:23 UTC
Study	Metabolic model analysis	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-08 08:42:57 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:18 UTC
Assay	Obtain metabolic model	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-08 08:43:02 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:08 UTC
Assay	Identify enzymes from spectra	Alan Williams	completed	2021-07-08 08:43:11 UTC	2021-07-08 08:43:14 UTC

Figure 22 Completed Project